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**SYNTHESIS OF METHYL-SUBSTITUTED
POLYPHENYLENESULFIDE FROM 2,4-
DICHLOROTOLUENE AND ITS FTIR SPECTROSCOPIC
ANALYSIS**

Sultanov Oybek

*Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Chemical Technology, Doctoral
Researcher*

E-mail: oybek__oybek@mail.ru

(ORCID: 0009-0002-4456-5647)

Tel: +998 95 313-79-90

Djalilov Abdulakhat

*Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Chemical Technology
Academician of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of
Chemical Sciences, Professor*

E-mail: gup_tniixt@mail.ru

Mustafayev, Muhammad-Ali

*Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Chemical Technology, Doctoral
Candidate*

E-mail: Muha1993ali1212@gmail.com

(ORCID: 0009-0005-4168-3383)

Abstract: *In this study, the synthesis of methyl-substituted polyphenylene sulfide (PFS) from 2,4-dichlorotoluene and sodium sulfide was performed via a high-temperature polycondensation process. The reaction was conducted in an N-methylpyrrolidone medium with a catalyst at 200–220°C, and its progression through the nucleophilic aromatic substitution (S_NAr)*

mechanism was scientifically substantiated. The molecular structure and functional groups of the resulting polymer were analyzed using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy.

Keywords: *polyphenylene sulfide, SNAr mechanism, FTIR spectroscopy, 2,4-dichlorotoluene, polycondensation, aromatic polymers, sulfide bonds, high-temperature synthesis, structural analysis, functional materials*

INTRODUCTION

In modern materials science, high-performance polymers, particularly those capable of operating at high temperatures and in aggressive chemical environments, are of great importance. Among this class of materials, polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) holds a significant position. PPS consists of macromolecules in which aromatic rings are linked by sulfide (–S–) bridges, resulting in a highly stable and ordered structure. This polymer possesses high thermal stability, is chemically inert, and mechanically strong, which accounts for its widespread use in fields such as automotive manufacturing, aerospace technology, electronics, and membrane systems. The traditional synthesis of PPS is based on p-dichlorobenzene. However, the properties of the polymer can be controlled by using substituted aromatic monomers. From this perspective, synthesis based on 2,4-dichlorotoluene is scientifically interesting and practically promising.

The molecular structure of polyphenylene sulfide has the following general structure.

Materials and Methods: The synthesis of methyl-substituted polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) from 2,4-dichlorotoluene and sodium sulfide is performed according to the following reaction equation.

The polycondensation process is carried out using 2,4-dichlorotoluene (C₇H₆Cl₂), sodium sulfide (Na₂S), and N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP) as a solvent, with a catalyst, at a reaction temperature of 200-220°C in an inert medium. The

resulting polymer exhibits the following properties: lower crystallinity, high elasticity, ease of processing, and preserved chemical stability.

The synthesis of methyl-substituted polyphenylene sulfide from 2,4-dichlorotoluene can be successfully achieved. The reaction proceeds via the SNAr mechanism and is effective at high temperatures and in the presence of a solvent. The electronic and steric effects of the methyl substituent significantly influence the polymer's structure, leading to a decrease in the material's crystallinity and an increase in its elasticity. Based on theoretical calculations, the maximum yield of the process is 3.05 g. The synthesis of a methyl-substituted polyphenylene sulfide analog from 2,4-dichlorotoluene and sodium sulfide, along with its structural properties, was analyzed using FTIR spectroscopy. The reaction was conducted in an N-methylpyrrolidone medium in the presence of a catalyst at a temperature of 200–220°C. The obtained results confirmed the formation of the polymer via the SNAr mechanism. In the FTIR spectrum, the aromatic ring, C–S bonds, and substituent groups were clearly identified. The analysis was performed using a SHIMADZU CORP. (Japan, 2017) model spectrometer. This instrument has a high sensitivity (signal-to-noise ratio of 60,000:1), enabling the precise analysis of various wavenumbers in samples despite the low intensity of the spectral lines. The measurement range covers the interval from 4000 to 450 cm^{-1} . To ensure the stable operation of the interferometer, an internal diagnostic system and an automatic drying device have been integrated, which provides for the long-term efficient performance of the instrument and a high level of user convenience.

Figure 1. FTIR spectroscopic analysis of polyphenylene sulfide synthesized from 2,4-dichlorotoluene.

FTIR (Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy) is a vital method for identifying functional groups within a polymer's composition. The structure of PFS, synthesized from 2,4-dichlorotoluene, is composed of aromatic rings and sulfide (-S-) bridges, and the spectrum reveals vibrations characteristic of these specific groups.

Table 1

Main Absorption Peaks of Polyphenylenesulfide Observed by FTIR Spectroscopy

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Peak type	Contact	Academic commentary
3344	Wide	O-H	Moisture
2918	Wide	C-H	Methyl group (from 2,4-dichlorotoluene)
1645	Medium	C=O / H ₂ O	Oxidation or adsorbed water
1509	Medium	C=C	Phenyl ring
1459-1410	Strong	C=C	Aromatic structure

1308–1205	Medium	C–S	Sulfide bonds
1160–1033	Strong	C–S / C–H	PPS-specific bonds
557–413	Strong	C–S / S–S	Sulfide chain

The 1509–1459 cm^{-1} range indicates the presence of phenyl rings, confirming the basic structure of PFS. The 1200–1000 cm^{-1} range, along with low peaks around 500 cm^{-1} , confirms the presence of sulfide bridges (C–S–C) formed as a result of this polymerization. The 872–744 cm^{-1} range confirms that the synthesis was based on 2,4-dichlorotoluene. The successful formation of the Cl \rightarrow S substitution reaction and the polymer chain is indicated.

CONCLUSION

The results of the FTIR spectroscopic analysis conclusively confirmed the molecular structure of the polymer. Specifically, aromatic vibrations in the 1500–1600 cm^{-1} range indicate the preservation of phenyl rings, while intense peaks in the 1200–1000 cm^{-1} range prove the formation of sulfide bonds. Furthermore, the low-frequency vibrations show the complete formation of the polymer backbone.

The presence of a methyl substituent affects the electronic structure of the polymer, slowing the kinetics of the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}\text{Ar}$ reaction but significantly altering the morphological properties of the final material. In particular, the decrease in the degree of crystallinity enhances the polymer's elasticity and processability.

Additionally, the extra functional groups (–OH, C=O) identified in the FTIR spectrum indicate that partial oxidation or modification processes have occurred on the polymer surface. This, in turn, increases the material's surface properties, notably its hydrophilicity and chemical reactivity.

As a result, the obtained polymer not only retains the properties of conventional PFS but also acquires new functional capabilities through modification. This makes it a promising candidate for use in membrane

technologies, ion-exchange systems, electrochemical devices, and for creating high-performance composite materials.

Overall, this research demonstrates that the properties of the material can be controlled through the synthesis of PPS based on substituted aromatic monomers. This approach serves as a crucial scientific platform for creating highly functional polymer materials in the future.

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